

Synthesis of new mesogens : 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)- β -benzoyl styrene

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Abstract : Homologous series 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)- β -benzoyl styrene have been synthesised and studied with a view to understand mesomorphic characteristics of the substances and their relation to the structure of the molecule. Methyl to hexyl derivatives are nonmesomorphic. Octyl and hexadecyl derivatives are monotropic nematic. Decyl, dodecyl and tetradecyl derivatives are enantiotropic, smectic and nematic. Odd-even effect is not observed. Nematic-isotropic and smectic-isotropic transition curves behaves in a normal manner. Thermal stabilities and mesomorphic characteristics are comparable with structurally related homologous series. Transition temperatures are observed through hot-stage polarizing microscope. Synthesis of homologous series was carried out by established method. Homologous series under discussion is partly smectogenic and partly nematogenic with middle ordered melting type. Nematic mesophase showed threaded texture while that of smectic mesophase bear focal conic fan shaped texture. Structure of the molecules are supported by analytical data. Transition temperatures are observed through hot stage polarizing microscope.

Keywords : Mesomorphism, smectic, nematic, liquid crystal.

Liquid crystalline state of matter is exploited in electronic display devices, medical instruments and many other fields of applications. Works was planned with a view to synthesize new liquid crystalline material. A number of ester homologous series with different molecular geometry are reported. The present new homologous series with two central bridges viz. -CH=CH-CO- and -COO- is reported.

Experimental

Preparation of the homologous series :

(a) *p-n*-Alkoxy benzoyl chlorides were prepared by the method of Vora and Dave^{1,2,6}.

(b) 4-Hydroxy chalcone was prepared by coupling 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde and acetophenone in presence of 50% KOH solution by the established method. The products were acidified by cold 1 : 1 HCl and washed with water, dried and crystallized in ethanol.

(c) *p-n*-Alkoxy benzoyl chlorides were condensed directly with 4-hydroxy chalcone. Ester formed were purified in alcohol^{3,4}. Analytical data supports the structure of the molecule.

Method of study :

The transition temperatures (Table 1) of the homologues are observed through a polarizing microscope provided with a heating stage.

Results and discussion

The chalcone linkage is not very conducive of exhibition of mesomorphism. However mesomorphism is induced by linking of a phenyl ring bridged through carboxylate central unit with *p*-substituted *n*-alkoxy group. The transition temperatures of a homologous series are shown in Table 1 and plotted versus the number of carbon atoms in *n*-alkyl chain. Phase diagram obtained is shown in the Fig. 1.

Table 1. Transition temperatures in °C

Sr. no.	<i>n</i> -AkyI group	Transition temp. (°C)		
		Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1.	Methyl	-	-	140.0
2.	Ethyl	-	-	172.0
3.	Propyl	-	-	146.0
4.	Butyl	-	-	116.0
5.	Pentyl	-	-	105.0
6.	Hexyl	-	-	118.0
7.	Octyl	-	(95.0)	106.0
8.	Decyl	94.0	111.0	126.0
9.	Dodecyl	85.0	106.0	131.0
10.	Tetradecyl	87.0	103.0	130.0
11.	Hexadecyl	-	(96.0)	106.0

() indicate monotropic.

Elemental analysis :

Sr. no.	R = <i>n</i> -alkyl chain	Molecular formula	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Obsd.)	
			C	H
1.	Methyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄	73.79 (73.68)	4.81 (4.91)
2.	Ethyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄	74.22 (74.13)	5.15 (5.22)
3.	Propyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₄	74.62 (74.52)	5.47 (5.59)
4.	Butyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₄	75.00 (74.95)	5.76 (5.82)
5.	Pentyl	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₄	75.34 (75.19)	6.04 (6.19)
6.	Hexyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₄	75.67 (75.52)	6.30 (6.39)
7.	Octyl	C ₃₀ H ₃₂ O ₄	76.27 (76.21)	6.77 (6.91)
8.	Decyl	C ₃₂ H ₃₆ O ₄	76.80 (76.61)	7.20 (7.32)
9.	Dodecyl	C ₃₄ H ₄₀ O ₄	77.27 (77.21)	7.57 (7.72)
10.	Tetradecyl	C ₃₆ H ₄₄ O ₄	77.69 (77.48)	7.91 (7.99)
11.	Hexadecyl	C ₃₈ H ₄₈ O ₄	78.08 (78.00)	8.21 (8.32)

Homologue	IR spectra (cm ⁻¹)
Hexyl	2854.5 cm ⁻¹ → Conforms alkyl group
	1654.8, 1211.2, 1164.9 cm ⁻¹ → Conform ester and keto group
	987.5 cm ⁻¹ → Conform trans sub. alkene
	810.0 cm ⁻¹ → <i>p</i> -disub. benzene ring
	694.3 and 775.3 cm ⁻¹ → mono sub. benzene ring
Octyl	2846.7 cm ⁻¹ → alkyl group
	1164.9, 1211.2, 1720.0 cm ⁻¹ → ester and keto group
	987.5 cm ⁻¹ → trans sub. alkene
	848.6 cm ⁻¹ → <i>p</i> -disub. benzene ring
	694.3 and 771.5 cm ⁻¹ → mono sub. benzene ring

 Fig. 1. 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)- β -benzoyl styrene.

The title homologous series is mesomorphic in nature. Methyl to hexyl derivatives are nonmesomorphic. Octyl and hexadecyl derivatives are monotropic nematic. Decyl, dodecyl and tetradecyl derivatives are enantiotropic, smectic and nematic simultaneously. The nematic-isotropic or vice versa and smectic-nematic transition curves behaves in a normal manner. The solid-mesomorphic or solid-isotropic transition curve follows a zig-zag path with less rising and more falling tendency. Odd-even effect is not observed in smectic-nematic and nematic-isotropic transition curves. The nematic mesophase is observed with threaded type of texture or droplets and smectic mesophase shows focal conic fan shaped texture as judged directly from the polarizing microscope. The molecular geometry of all members in the title homologous series are common. Three phenyl rings linked through -COO- and -CH=CH-CO- bridges are commonly present in the homologous series. Therefore, the overall polarity, polarizability, aromaticity, π -electron density etc. related to adhering intermolecular forces of attractions operates equally. But mesomorphic property and degree of mesomorphism from homologue to homologue in same series varies with varying alkyl chain of *n*-alkoxy group.

The average thermal stabilities and the stage of commencement of smectic mesophase for the homologous series which is a structurally similar, selected for comparative study are as below :

Series	(1)	(A)
Smectic-isotropic or smectic-nematic	106.66 (C ₁₀ -C ₁₆)	114.0 (C ₁₀ -C ₁₆)
Commencement of smectic mesophase	C ₁₀	C ₁₀
Nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic	119.8 (C ₈ -C ₁₀)	138.54 (C ₁ -C ₈)
Commencement of nematic mesophase	C ₈	C ₁

4-(4'-n-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-phenylazo benzenes

The molecular geometry of both the homologous series under comparison is common with respect to three phenyl rings, central bridge -COO- and left n -alkoxy group, but they differ in other central bridge i.e. -CH=CH-CO- and -N=N- respectively. Therefore mesomorphic properties and degree of mesomorphism depend upon the varying central bridge joining middle and third phenyl ring without any substitution. Thus intermolecular forces of attractions vary according to effect caused to the aromaticity, polarity, polarizability, length to breadth ratio etc. The smectic-isotropic/smectic-nematic thermal stability as well as nematic-isotropic or vice versa thermal stability of homologous series (A) are higher than the title homologous series (1). This suggests that intermolecular forces of attractions amongst the molecules of series (A) are strengthened by replacing -CH=CH-CO- to -N=N- as second central bridge -CH=CH-CO- is relatively longer and weaker than -N=N- . Electronegativity of carbon is less than nitrogen. Moreover each nitrogen atom joined with double bond carry lone pair of electrons while two carbons joined with double bond does not carry the same. Therefore electronic interactions in case of -N=N- creates stronger intermolecular attractions and induces more rigid nature to the molecules of series (A). Thus group efficiency order as derived on the basis of thermal stability with respect to central bridges -CH=CH-CO- and -N=N- is as under.

Smectic group : $\text{-N=N-} > \text{-CH=CH-CO-}$
efficiency order

Nematic group : $\text{-N=N-} > \text{-CH=CH-CO-}$
efficiency order

Early or late commencement of smectic mesophase depend upon the noncoplanarity caused by the molecules. Both series under comparison shows that smectic mesophase commences from tenth homologue. This suggests that noncoplanarity caused by -N=N- and -CH=CH-CO- is equivalent. Commencement of nematic mesophase in series (A) takes place from very first member of the series while it occurs from eighth homologue for series (1). This suggests that intermolecular forces of attractions are imbalanced by the -CH=CH-CO- group in such a way that, on heating the crystal of the substance, statistically parallel orientations of molecules maintained from very first homologue in case of series (A), while molecules of the title homologous series are randomly oriented directly to isotropic liquid without passing through mesomorphic state upto sixth member of the series i.e. nematic mesophase commences from eighth homologue.

Conclusions : New homologous series with -COO- and -CH=CH-CO- central bridges have been synthesized by treating p - n -alkoxy benzoyl chloride with 4-hydroxy chalcone. Series is partly nematic and partly smectic in character. Group efficiency order derived by comparing mesogenic properties with other series.

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